

USE OF TECHNOLOGICAL TOOLS IN TEACHER EDUCATION: A PREFERENCE STUDY

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Abstract

Technological Tools are becoming an integral part of education, used to enhance the Quality, Accessibility, and Effectiveness of the Teaching-Learning Process. By employing these tools, the classroom learning becomes more interactive and engaging. These facilitate personalized learning by involving the students in learning. It also promotes collaboration and effective communication. There are many technological tools that can be used by Teachers. The education system in India is still in its transitional stage, so the integration of such tools in schools and institutions could be helpful for teachers and students to enjoy the perks of blended learning. Therefore, the present study was planned to examine the preferences of pupil teachers and pupil teacher educators for the technological tools used in the field of education. Edrawmind, Edpuzzle, Mentimeter, and Plickers have been identified for the study. A qualitative research approach has been adopted for the present study, in which experience-based participatory observation of the pupil teachers and pupil teacher educators has been done. The data has been collected from 20 pupil teachers and pupil teacher educators selected through a convenience sampling technique. The objective of the study was to find out the preferences of pupil teachers and teacher educators for the use of four identified tools, Edrawmind, Edpuzzle, Mentimeter, and Plickers, based on their utility and feasibility. The present paper highlights the preferences, appropriateness, and relevance of the identified technological tools to use in the teaching-learning process. The study also reveals the features that contributed to the identified tool being the most preferred technological tool.

Keywords: Educational Technological Tools (ETT), ICT Tools, Preference, Edrawmind, Plickers, Mentimeter, Edpuzzle, Pupil Teachers.

Introduction:

Education is the process of exchanging knowledge and information that brings about behaviour change. Back in the day when education was teacher-centered, these changes were brought through traditional teaching and learning methods like lecturing, chalk and talk methods, etc. Now, Technology has turned out to be a successful catalyst in transforming the education system. It is experienced in an entirely different manner both by students and by teachers, where the way of acquisition and transmission of information and knowledge has completely changed due to Technological Integration. Technology will not find its use in education unless they are actually used by teachers. There is a wide range of Technological Tools available, ranging from interactive software and multimedia platforms to online collaborative tools, ICT Tools, Ed-Tech Apps, AI Tools, etc, that have empowered educators to create dynamic lessons and ensure maximum student learning. These technological tools are used by the teachers to create a Learner-Centered and Tech-Enabled Environment in the classroom. Such Technological Tools have facilitated teachers in giving personalized learning experiences, encouraged students' engagement, student-teachers' and teacher-teacher' collaboration, real-time assessment facility, etc. The incorporation of Technological Tools within the educational ecosystem requires maximum utilization of both Hardware Tools (computers, mobile devices, projectors, IWB, etc) and Software Tools (educational applications, web browsers, mobile applications, etc) by the Teachers. They play a very important role in effective incorporation of technologies in the classroom. Teachers have a strong and growing preference for incorporating technology into their classrooms, according to recent studies and reports from 2025. The acknowledged advantages of technology in improving engagement, individualizing learning, and expediting administrative and instructional duties are what are driving this trend. Their level of expertise with the technological tools will determine their level of acceptance of the integration (Sharma, 2021). NEP 2020 also imagines delivering education through online/digital media. But, the benefits of online/digital education cannot be leveraged unless the digital divide is eliminated (NEP 2020, *para.* 24.2.). As technological tools are the future of education and there is an on-going search to get suitable equipment that will be made available to teachers at schools so that teachers can suitably integrate e-contents into teaching-learning practices (NEP 2020, *para.* 23.6.). Study helps to gain understanding about the inclination of teachers for Technological

Tool. Studies have been conducted to analyze how educators view the use of technological resources in terms of the advantages and disadvantages of integrating them, as well as their general disposition toward the use of technology in teaching and learning activities (De Maria, 2025). Study conducted on 418 as a sample explores teachers the preference of primary teachers through a Discrete Choice Model (DCM) revealed that preferences are greatly affected by the interactivity of e-resources (Kostaki & Linardakis, 2025). A study conducted on 1102 students from two universities, to find students' attitudes towards Technology and also find their choice for learning tools revealed that students gravitate towards the blend of Traditional and digital tools for achieving their learning goals (Andrew *et.al.*, 2018). Another study conducted to identify students' and teachers' preferences for technologies that they want to use for learning and teaching revealed that there are clashes in choices, as the teachers chose course learning Technology while students rely on traditional methodology (Buzzard *et.al.*, 2011). Thus, the presented study aimed to Identify the Preferences of Students of Teacher Education Programme for the Use of Identified Technological Tools in the Educational Ecosystem.

Methodology:

A Qualitative Research Approach has been employed to regulate the study. A sample of 20 students from Teacher Education Programmes studying at Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna University (H.N.B.G.U.), Srinagar, Uttarakhand, was selected through a purposive and convenience sampling technique. The sample includes participants from the I.T.E.P. course, B.Ed. course and from the M.Ed. course. A more informed understanding of the respondents' experience with the identified technological tools is gathered through Participatory Observation. For getting better insights, the observation has been done, keeping following areas in mind namely 'Content Creation in Tool', 'Tool Proficiency and Usage', 'Competency to Perform Tool-Specific Task', and 'Comprehending Data Analytics'. Four Technological Tools, namely, Edrawmind, Edpuzzle, Mentimeter, and Plickers, have been identified that are to be used in study. These Tools hold specific potential in the Educational Ecosystem. Edrawmind is a Cross-Platform Mind-Mapping and Brainstorming Tool that helps to improve productivity and organize thoughts. Edpuzzle is an Interactive Video Creation Tool that helps to ensure student accountability while watching videos. Mentimeter (or Menti) is an Online Teaching Tool where teachers can create engaging presentations with

interactive activities for students. Similarly, Plickers is an Educational Tool used for Formative Assessment of students without needing to have individual devices in the classroom. After the Identification of the Technological Tools, a 5-day Orientation Session was organized for participants, wherein Knowledge of the Tool was gained by the participants through a Demo. On the 5th day of Orientation Session, queries regarding tools were taken, and accounts for the interested student were created on each tools so that they begin their practices. The Duration for Practice on the Technological Tool by future teachers was 25 days. At end of the practice session, an Interview was conducted to know their preference of Identified Technological Tools, and accordingly, the responses were marked on the basis of ranking.

Results:

Table No. 1: Preferences of Sample for Identified Technological Tool.

Edrawmind	Edpuzzle	Mentimeter	Plickers
2.25	3.2	2.75	1.8

Table No. 1 presents the average score regarding Preferences of Sample (i.e. I.T.E.P, B.Ed. and M.Ed) for Identified Technological Tool. A Low Score indicates Greater Preference, whereas a High Score indicates Lesser Preference for the Identified Technological Tool. Plickers is first preferred tool with average score of 1.8. Plickers is accepted due its unique feature called Plicker's Response Cards. In Plickers, the Pupil Teacher and Pupil Teacher Educators created their own class, Created Question Sets, performed the Task of scanning through Plickers App, and were able to comprehend analytics generated for each question. EdrawMind is second preferred tool with average score of 2.25. Participants used Edrawmind quite easily, participants made use of features like creating Mindmaps through AI feature, the Brainstorming feature and the Collaboration feature were very much liked by participants. Mentimeter is third preferred tool with average score of 2.7. Participants created presentations from scratch and also used AI feature of Mentimeter They were able to Run or 'present' their Menti and access pre-made templates. The Edpuzzle got an average score of 3.2 making it as fourth preferred Identified Technological Tool. The main features used by participants in Edpuzzle tool are browsing, Editing of Pre-Existing Teacher -developed content, Integrated Interactive Elements in Videos, added audio Notes and assigning their Video during practice.

Fig.-1: Preferences of Sample for Identified Technological Tools.

Fig.1 shows that the sample gave highest preference to Plickers and lowest to Edpuzzle.

Table No. 2: Preferences of I.T.E.P. Participants’ for Identified Technological Tool.

EdrawMind	Edpuzzle	Mentimeter	Plickers
3	3.5	2.5	1

Table No. 2 presents the average score regarding Preferences of I.T.E.P. Participants’ for Identified Technological Tool. Plickers is first preferred tool with average score of 1. Mentimeter is second preferred tool with average score of 2.5. Edrawmind is the third preferred tool with average score of 3 and Edpuzzle got an average score of 3.5 making it as fourth preferred Identified Technological Tool.

Fig.2: Preferences of I.T.E.P. Participants’ for Identified Technological Tool.

Fig.2 shows that the I.T.E.P. Participants gave highest preference to Plickers and lowest preference for Edpuzzle.

Table No. 3: Preferences of B.Ed. Participants' for Identified Technological Tool.

EdrawMind	Edpuzzle	Mentimeter	Plickers
1.9	2.8	3.1	2.2

Table No. 3 presents the average score regarding Preferences of B.Ed. Participants' for Identified Technological Tool. Edrawmind is first preferred tool with average score of 1.9. Plickers is second preferred tool with average score of 2.2. Edpuzzle is the third preferred tool with average score of 2.8 and the Mentimeter got an average score of 3.1 making it as fourth preferred Identified Technological Tool.

Fig.3: Preferences of B.Ed. Participants' for Identified Technological Tool.

Fig.3 shows that the B.Ed Participants' gave highest preference to Edrawmind and lowest preference to Mentimeter.

Table No. 4: Preferences of M.Ed. Participants' for Identified Technological Tool.

EdrawMind	Edpuzzle	Mentimeter	Plickers
2	4	2	2

Table No. 4 presents the average score regarding Preferences of M.Ed. Participants' for Identified Technological Tool. It indicates that M.Ed. participants have equal preferences for three identified tools namely Edrawmind, Mentimeter and Plickers. Each of the three Tools has an average score of 2. Mentimeter is second preferred tool with average score of 2.5.

Fig.4: Preferences of M.Ed. participants' for Identified Technological Tool.

Fig.4 shows that the M.Ed participants' gave equal preferences to Plickers, Mentimeter and Edrawmind tools. They gave second preference to Edpuzzle.

Discussion:

The study reveals that the pupil teachers and pupil teacher educators selected Plickers because it allows greater practicality in the context of Indian classroom teaching; they found creating assessment sheets in the tool a hassle-free task. Teachers reported they prefer resources that promote inclusive education, like apps for differentiated instruction or accessibility features that cater to a range of learning needs and disabilities. They are aware that the teacher at every stage of the lesson presentation has an urge to check student learning and wants to assess to fulfillment of lesson objectives. They found that this tool helped them boost their confidence in using technology, and they are looking forward to implementing it in their own classroom to ensure active participation of students. Plickers can be used in both online and offline modes, and its Response card feature is the main reason for its high preference among most pupil teachers and teacher educators. It has offered great ease to practicing future Teacher in Creating Worksheet for students' assessment. This tool has a Plickers Mobile app for both android and ios gave participants access through mobile phones as well as Laptops etc to future teacher that's why Plicker became first-choice. The tool has much potential to offer its benefits irrespective of the geographical makeup of the school. Based on their participants practice on these tools, Edrawmind, Edpuzzle and Mentimeter,

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they reported that operating them requires high-speed, 24*7 Internet connectivity and 1:1 computer or device availability to all students as well as teachers, which is quite a challenging task in a hilly area like Srinagar, Uttarakhand. They found that the data analytics generated on Edpuzzle, Mmentimeter and Plickers were very easy to comprehend for both teachers and students. They particularly found that Plickers provide an opportunity for participants to initiate discussions with students. All three identified tool except Plickers were purely Online-based tools, participants were found skeptical for its implementation in classroom and a low consistency of used is observed. Participants found themselves diffident in using Edpuzzle due to its complex interface. Despite difficulties faced by them, participants showed inclination towards technological tools and are surely looking forwards to Uitlising Modern technological tool for improving their Teaching as well as Technical skills

Conclusion:

Technology is the discussion of the current times, with endless possibilities to offer in the field of education. NEP 2020, with a prime focus on transforming the Indian Education System, requires all Pre- Service Teachers and In-Service Teachers to Integrate Technology and Technological Tools in the classroom to provide high-quality content, utilize available educational resources, and implement an efficient feedback mechanism. There is a wide array of technological tools that are developed for teachers to utilize, and teachers, in order to foster a positive attitude towards such technological tools, are looking for tools that have less difficulty, ones that fully suit their purpose, and have fewer technical difficulties. Use of Plickers and other similar Technological Tools should be increased for effective assessment of Teachers' Intention of lesson delivery and to assess students' learning. The study conducted on pre-service teachers reveals that Plickers has more advantages to offer than disadvantages. Plickers allows teachers to prepare and apply assessment sheets in the classroom quite easily (Galip Öner, 2023). Therefore, the Use of Technological Tools must be increased in parallel with Building Intention of Teachers to utilize Technology and its Technological Innovation in their Teaching practices.

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